

3-Bromoflavone (8a-e); To a solution of cupric bromide (1g) in ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture (2:1), chromone (0.3 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed until gray-white precipitate of cuprous bromide was obtained (6-12 h). It was then filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent. The yield, m.p. and solvent of crystallisation were as follows: **8a** (80%), m.p. 103°; δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 3.2 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 7.2-8.6 (6H, m, ArH); **8b** (75%), m.p. 93° (EtOH); **8c** (82%), m.p. 71-72° (MeOH); **8d** (70%), m.p. 59° (EtOH); **8e** (90%), m.p. 112°.

Coumaran-3-ones (5a-e) (Scheme 2): A mixture of the 3-bromochromone (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) and ethanolic KOH (70 ml; 25%) was gently refluxed for 2 h. The solution was then poured into ice/HCl (2N). The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised: **5a** (70%), **5b** (85%), **5c** (65%), **5d** (75%) and **5e** (85%).

The products showed no depression on admixture (1:1) with coumaran-3-ones obtained by the other route (Scheme 1).

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Studies on Flavonoids. Part-II. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 8-Bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones

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CONSIDERING the therapeutic and synthetic importance of flavonoids¹, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new flavonoids and evaluate their antimicrobial activity.

The present work reports the synthesis of 8-bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones (2), -flavonols (3) and -flavanones (4). These are derived from previously synthesised² 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1) which have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-butoxy-5-nitroacetophenone and various aromatic aldehydes and tested for their antimicrobial activity².

The chalcones (1) on oxidation with selenium dioxide in n-amyl alcohol³ were smoothly converted into the flavones (2). The chalcones (1) when subjected to Alger-Flynn-Oyamada oxidation⁴ using alkaline hydrogen peroxide gave the flavonols (3). Cyclisation⁵ of the chalcones (1) in ethanol in presence of sulphuric acid (10%) yielded the corresponding flavanones (4) (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectra. The compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities at a concentration of 50 μg by cup-plate method⁶ against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungus *Aspergillus niger*, and were compared with chloromycetin, penicillin G and streptomycin. The compounds showed strong activity (15-25 mm, zone of inhibition) against *S. aureus*, and medium or weak activity (6-15 mm) against *E. coli*. Most of the compounds were found strongly active (15-30 mm) against *A. niger*. It is concluded that some of the compounds containing chlorine atom/atoms introduced in aryl part of the flavonoid molecule were found to be most active, while the others possess moderate or weak activity against both bacteria and fungi.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compl. no.	R	Mol formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₆ NBr	132	60
2b	2'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	105	70
2c	4'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	97	65
2d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ NCI ₂ Br	145	75
2e	4'-Methylphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	90	60
2f	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ NBr	200	62
2g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₈ NBr	160	66
2h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₇ NBr	215	60
2i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	100	65
2j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	125	58
2k	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₂ Br	102	50
2l	4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₇ NBr	110	45
3a	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₆ NBr	140	70
3b	2'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	170	80
3c	4'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	185	78
3d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ NCI ₂ Br	162	85
3e	4'-Methylphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	152	68
3f	4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ NBr	195	65
3g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₈ NBr	115	70
3h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₇ NBr	130	65
3i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	112	70
3j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	160	60
3k	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₂ Br	124	65
3l	4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₇ NBr	80	50
4a	Phenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₆ NBr	116	75
4b	2'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	160	80
4c	4'-Chlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ NCIBr	185	80
4d	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₆ NCI ₂ Br	220	82
4e	4'-Methylphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	150	60
4f	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₇ NBr	140	65
4g	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₈ NBr	180	58
4h	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₇ NBr	190	65
4i	4'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	120	70
4j	2'-Methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆ NBr	110	50
4k	4'-N-Dimethylaminophenyl	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₂ Br	90	50
4l	4'-Hydroxy-3'-methoxyphenyl	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₇ NBr	75	45

*Elemental analyses found satisfactory.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The IR spectra of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a XL-100 A (100.1 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc.

8-Bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitroflavones (2a): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; 1 g) and SeO₂ (1 g) in dry n-amyl alcohol (15–20 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130–40° for 24 h. Selenium metal was filtered and the filtrate was steam-distilled to remove n-amyl alcohol. The brownish solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 132° (Found: C, 54.60; H, 3.78; N, 3.38. C₁₉H₁₆O₆NBr calcd. for: C, 54.54; H, 3.82; N, 3.35%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1630 (C=O), 1555 (C=C), 1130 (C–O–C) and 550 cm⁻¹ (CBr); δ (TMS; DMSO-d₆) 4.5 (9H, m, 7-OC₄H₉), 6.60 (1H, s, 3-H), 7.0–7.7 (m, ArH) and 7.85 (1H, s, 5-H).

Similarly, other substituted flavones were prepared (2b–l; Table 1).

8-Bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitroflavonols (3a): Compound 1 (0.5 g) in methanol (15 ml) was treated with sodium hydroxide (15 ml; 10%) and hydrogen peroxide (4 ml; 18%). The mixture was kept in an ice-bath for 2 h and left overnight at room temperature. It was then poured into ice-water and acidified. The resulting solid was crystallised from methanol, (70%), m.p. 140° (Found: C, 52.58; H, 3.75; N, 3.16. C₁₉H₁₆O₆NBr calcd. for: C, 52.53; H, 3.68; N, 3.22%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3300 (OH), 1610 (C=O), 1560 (C=C), 1085 (C–O–C) and 560 cm⁻¹ (CBr); δ 4.45 (9H, m, 7-OC₄H₉), 7.0–7.7 (m, ArH) and 7.85 (1H, s, 5-H).

Similarly, other flavonols were prepared (3b–l; Table 1).

8-Bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitroflavanone (4a): A mixture of 1 (0.5 g) in ethanol (30 ml) and aqueous H₂SO₄ (20 ml; 10%) was refluxed for 24 h on a water-bath and then distilled to remove ethanol and filtered while hot and left at room temperature. The resulting solid was crystallised from petroleum ether, (75%), m.p. 116° (Found: C, 54.35; H, 4.24; N, 3.35. C₁₉H₁₈O₆NBr calcd. for: C, 54.28; H, 4.28; N, 3.33%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 1690 (C=O), 1110

(C-O-C) and 555 cm^{-1} (CBr); δ 2.60 (2H, d, 3-H), 4.40 (9H, m, 7-OC₄H₉), 5.20 (1H, m, 2-H), 7.0-7.6 (m, ArH) and 7.80 (1H, s, 5-H).

Similarly, other flavanones were prepared (4b-1; Table 1).

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Synthesis of Cyclic Ketones by Activated Nitriles†

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THE use of cyano compounds in organic synthesis is now receiving considerable interest. As a part of our program of developing new, simple and efficient procedure for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds using readily available nitrile-containing intermediates¹⁻⁶, the synthesis of cyclohexan-1,3-dione derivatives using acrylonitrile as starting material has now been achieved and is reported herein.

Thus, when acrylonitrile was treated with the ketones (1a-d) in alkaline medium a product (2) was

obtained whose structure was assigned on the basis of its conversion to the semicarbazone derivatives (4). Hydrolysis and estrification in one-step reaction of δ -ketonitriles (2a-d) resulted in the formation of the corresponding δ -ketoester (5a-d). Structure 5 was established based on elemental analysis and ir spectrum which showed well-defined bands attributable for C=O (ester at 1710 and ketonic at 1690 cm^{-1}). The δ -ketoester (5) was readily cyclised into cyclohexan-1,3-dione derivatives (6) on heating with alcoholic sodium methoxide. Structure 6 was confirmed by analytical and ir spectral data which showed well-defined bands at 1740 cm^{-1} attributable to cyclic C=O. The structures of 6 were further confirmed by preparing (i) the 2-phenylazo derivatives (7a, b, d) in three cases (from 6a, b, d, respectively), (ii) bis-(2,6-diketo-3-phenylcyclohexyl) methane (8) by condensing with benzaldehyde and (iii) the 2-bromo derivative (9) by bromination of 6d.

The cyanoethylation reaction of the ketones (1) with acrylonitrile can be considered as a novel route for the synthesis of not only cyclic ketones but also for the synthesis of bicyclic ketones. Thus, it was found that heating of cyclohexanone-2-methylpropionate in alcoholic sodium methoxide afforded bicyclo[1,3,3]nonan-2,9-dione (10). Structure 10 was established on the basis of analytical and spectral data, which showed band at 1740 cm^{-1} (CO).

Experimental

4-Phenyl-4-acetylbutyronitrile (2d): Sodium metal (0.46 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in benzyl methyl ketone (100 g, 0.7 mol) at 90° , then acrylonitrile (28 g, 0.52 mol) was added dropwise within 20 min at $50-60^\circ$. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min, then cooled and neutralised with glacial acetic acid (3 ml) and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was dried and the solvent evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product (69%), b.p. $160-61^\circ/10\text{ mm}$ (lit.⁶ $170-72^\circ/12\text{ mm}$); semicarbazone derivative (4d), m.p. 160° (ethanol).

Methyl 4-phenyl-4-acetylbutyrate (5d): A mixture of 2d (0.4 mol) and anhydrous methanol (200 ml) saturated with dry HCl gas was stirred and left to stand overnight, then cooled to 0° , diluted with water and extracted with benzene. The organic layer was washed in turn with water, 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure to give the product (60%), b.p. $142-44^\circ/4\text{ mm}$ (lit.⁶ $112-14^\circ/0.1\text{ mm}$).

Similarly, the methyl ester of 4-acetylbutyronitrile⁷, 4-acetylvaleronitrile⁸ and 4-acetyl-4-propylbutyronitrile⁹ were prepared (Table 1).

4-Phenylcyclohexan-1, 3-dione (6d): To a solution of sodium methoxide (0.05 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was added 5d (0.05 mol) and refluxed with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was cooled, neutralised with H_2SO_4 (30 ml; 2N) and the excess methanol

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